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Handloom Industry in India with Special Reference to Jammu and Kashmir

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to travel around the study of handloom industry in India and in Jammu and Kashmir and also defines its role in employment generation. This paper is mainly based on the secondary data which is collected from books, journals and from different social and academic websites. The mentioned study established that handloom industry is spread in all over the India and provide employment near about forty three lack persons and also plays an important role in economic development both in rural and urban economy. The paper also focussed that the growth performance of handloom industry in Jammu and Kashmir It's our anxiety to increase this labour intensive industry for generation of more income and employment.

Keywords: handloom Industry, economic development, employment, weavers. Growth performance of handloom industry in Jammu and Kashmir

Introduction

India is one of the major creator support of financial nature and implementation of various development programmes and schemes helped the Handloom Market for economic growth and development. In this paper the role of handloom sector in the Indian economy and schemes provided by the Government as well as various competitive strategies have been discussed. The handloom items which got its imaginative and heritage importance in our nation. This sector is cottage based or house hold industry and also got much importance in rural economy in India. This sector is also eco-friendly with nature. Apart from this it provides employment to 43 lack persons which means huge contribution come from this sector with less investment and also it give full opportunity for women workers. In our country there is large number of unemployed youth which by the efforts of government can be absorbed by this industry if it can be flourished because it is labour intensive in nature. Government of India after independence has been consequently using various polices to boost the handloom sector through different policies programmes and schemes. The handloom sector of India is also one of the mainly export contributor for country's economy, which added at least 13.25 % of the exports in our nation. The Handloom industries of Jammu and Kashmir provides vast employment potential to millions of rural and urban folks and bring unique improvement in the quality of life. The distinguishing selling point of the Handloom sector is that it is highly labour intensive industry with low capital investment. It is also

a low energy sector with no unfavourable impact on the environment as handloom weaving is a totally pollution free activity. Handloom is an important cottage industry in our country has special socio-economic significance due to its massive potential for economic activities like the generation of employment and income. The handloom sectors are significant vehicles for meeting the economic growth and equity with social justice objectives of developing economies. Handloom industrial sector also help in generating large scale employment, mobilizing advanced skill and resources, enhancing entrepreneurship, energizing village economies aiding the process of backward areas development and performing an important role in the overall process of industrialization. The handloom industry in Jammu And Kashmir State is centuries old known for its specific weaving of handloom products like, pashmina, Raffal, silk sarees and cotton items. The handloom development department plays a pivotal role in modernization of handloom industry in the state through skill up-gradation of weavers by providing modernized looms, training, designing and weaving.

Objectives

- To study the overall view of handloom industry in India in general and particular in Jammu and Kashmir.
- To understand the role of handloom industry in the economic development in India.
- To analyze the growth performance of handloom development cooperation in Jammu and Kashmir.

Methodology

The data for the present study has been collected from secondary sources, books, journals, newspapers, published and unpublished research work, various search engines, are also used.

Result and Discussions

The handloom sector is that type of industry which wants skilled labour less capital investment and generate well proposition of employment and income. It depicts the richness of Indian culture and also provides the livelihood to thousands of people directly or indirectly both in rural and urban economy in India. Handloom industry in India gets its name and fame from very beginning and it also has its historical importance in India. The handloom textile industry of India and in Jammu and Kashmir is much famed both in national as well as in international markets due to its creative nature. This sector desires skilled labour which India got from inheritance. In an overpopulated country like India its labour intensive nature does well to balance the unemployment ratio. Handloom industrial sector also help in generating huge employment, mobilizing advanced skill and resources, enhancing entrepreneurship, energizing village economies aiding the process of backward areas development and performing an important role in the overall process of industrialization. It is also a low energy sector with no adverse impact on the environment as weaving is a totally pollution free activity. The sector has an edge over the power loom on mill sectors in its ability to commercially produce the

goods in small volumes, openness to innovations, switch over to new designs, adaptability to suit suppliers requirements and creation of exquisite designs. Handlooms have a great potential in this regard as they hold the key not only for sustaining the existing craft persons but for providing gainful employment, both full-time and part-time, to increasingly larger sections of the economically poor and dispossessed weavers. The handloom sector has been playing a significant role in providing employment to several lakhs of rural and urban people; Village and cottage industries to which the handloom sector belongs are oriented towards balanced socio-economic development of the state owing to the built in mechanism that encourages weavers and craftsmen to seek an honourable place in the society. Handloom is one such industry which can be recognized both in urban and rural areas regardless of the availability of modern infrastructural facilities. Handloom sector in India is best known for its uniqueness, Style, conventionality and modern technology. Each and every state in India has the capability of boasting innovative printing, weaving, embroidery and designing trends. And it is this art form that gives them their individuality. What makes the handloom industry significant is the use of fine textured fabrics, exclusively beautiful patterns, trendy outlook and sheer finesse in the product. In fact, handloom industry has tried its hands on almost every product that can be thought off. From saris to suits, lehngas, skirts, stoles, scarfs, shawls, jackets and many more handloom industry in India has flourished to a large extent. This industry is scattered in all over the country as show in below table 1.1.

Table No.1.1: state wise details of Handloom Units, Workers and looms

State	Number of units	Number of handloom weavers and allied workers	Number of handlooms/ products
Assam	1240817	1643453	1111577
West Bengal	406761	779103	307829
Tamil Nadu	189069	352321	154509
Manipur	178975	218753	190634
Andhara Pradesh	176996	355838	124714
Tripura	120652	137177	139011
Uttar Pradesh	110542	257783	80295
Naga land	60891	66490	47088
Orissa	40683	114106	43652
Mizoram	39499	43528	24136
Karnataka	37680	89256	40488
Arunachal Pradesh	30343	33041	27286
Bihar	25485	43392	14973
Rajasthan	22668	31958	5403
Jammu and Kashmir	17293	33209	7301
Jharkhand	14178	21160	2128
Kerla	11690	14679	13097
Meghalaya	11400	13612	8967

Madhya pradesh	8691	14761	3604
Himachal pradesh	7006	13458	5578
Haryana	6455	7967	4876
Gujrat	3676	11009	3900
Chhattisgarh	2664	8191	2471
Punjab	2377	2636	261
Maharashtra	1977	3418	4511
Delhi	1875	2738	2560
Pondicherry	1754	2803	1771
Skim	568	568	345
All India	2783271	4331876	2377331

Source: handloom census report of 2009-10

In the above table 1.1 it has been seen that the handloom industry is spread in whole country and it provides the employment to large number of weavers. It has also shown in the above table that different states and union territories, the units of handloom industry has be fully flourished for production of different and famous handloom textiles. Assam, Manipur, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, Tripura, Andhra Pradesh has got much handloom units as per censes 2009-10, which means that this sector has deep rooted these states and also got an economic importance.

Figure 1.1.: State wise Number of handloom weavers and allied workers

Figure 1.1 shows that handloom industry in different states and the weavers who got the job from this sector. Some of the main states where this industry provides the satisfactory employment to weavers and other allied workers directly or indirectly are Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Manipur Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, Assam and Tripura.

Table 1.2: state wise Distribution of handloom worker households.

States/UTs	Total handloom worker household	Percent distribution	Share%total households in state
		44.58	21.7
Assam	1,241	14.61	2.1
West Bengal	407	6.79	1.2
Tamil Nadu	189	6.43	33.7
Manipur	179	6.36	1.0
Andhara pradesh	177	4.33	17.6
Tripura	121	3.97	0.4
Uttar pradesh	111	2.19	9.7
Naga land	61	1.46	0.5
Orissa	41	1.42	18.9
Mizoram	39	1.35	0.3
Karnatka	38	1.09	12.7
Arunchal pradesh	30	0.92	0.2
Bihar	25	0.81	0.2
Rajasthan	23	0.62	0.8
Jammuand Kashmir	17	0.51	0.3
Jharkhand	14	0.42	0.1
Kerla	12	0.41	2.3
Maghalaya	11	0.38	0.6
Uttaranchal	11	0.31	0.1
Madhya pradesh	9	0.25	0.5
Hiamchal pradesh	7	0.23	0.1
Haryana	6	0.13	0.0
Gujrat	4	0.10	0.1
Chhattisgarh	3	0.09	0.0
Punjab	2	0.07	0.0
Maharashtra	2	0.07	0.0
Delhi	2	0.06	0.7
Pondicherry	2	0.02	0.5
Skim	1		
All india	2,783	100.0	1.26

Source: Handloom Census Report 2009-10

In the above table 1.2 it has been that the Assam alone accounts for 12.41 lakh (44.6%) handloom households, whereas Manipur and Tripura have 1.79 lakh (4.3%) such household, respectively. Other states

with comparatively large concentrations are: west Bengal: 4.07 lakh (14.6%) Andhra Pradesh: 1.77 lakh (6.4%) Tamil Nadu: 1.89 lakh (6.8%) Uttar Pradesh: 1.11 lakh (4.0%).

Table 1.3 the growth performance of Handloom industry in Jammu and Kashmir state handloom Development Corporation as shown in below table.

Year	Production(Rs.in Lakh)	Sales(Rs in Lakh)	Growth%	
			production	sales
2008-09	4001.32	5016.66	-	-
2009-10	1055.67	4970.87	-73.6	-0.91
2010-11	2009.51	15269.50	90.3	207.1
2011-12	2185.93	25835.42	8.77	69.1
2012-13	2576.50	3138.75	17.8	-87.8

Source: Digest of Statistics 2012-13

The table indicates that the annual growth rate of production was -73.6 during 2009-10 which has negative while it was highly increased to 90.3% during 2010-11. The growth rate of production was again decreased to 8.77% during 2011-12 and then it was increased to 17.8% during 2012-13

The table also indicates that the annual growth rate of sales showed fluctuations. The growth rate of sales during 2009-10 was -0.91 which is negative and it was highly increased to 207.1% during 2010-11. but the growth rate was again decreased to 69.1% during 2011-12 and during 2012-13 the growth rate again showed negative growth rate of -87.8 There are many reasons for the lower growth rate of handloom industry such as appropriate financial assistance is not available to have the stock of raw materials like yarn, zari materials for the weavers to work incessantly further the raw materials are provided by the private dealers with high costs. Working capital is the main source for mainting a industry but in handloom sector working capital is also a main crisis so handloom weavers become unable to purchase the raw material even at the decling prices. The quantity, quality and regularity in the supply in raw materials are all quite unsatisfactory. Adequate production of yarn consumed by handloom weavers is not forthcoming. The high prices of yarn makes it uneconomic for the weavers to buy it. The inferior quality of the yarn shaped for the handloom weavers and heavy transport cost as the yarn formed in one region is being consumed by the weavers in other region also adds to weavers problems. Dyes and chemicals which are used in the production of handloom cloth are not very frequently available in time and their quality is also not acceptable. the commodities have been facing increasing competition in world markets It is an established fact that Political insatiability of any kind and any of nature has always a long impact on economies and production of handlooms of the world. Similarly slow development and low production of handloom industry is attributed towards political instability in Jammu and Kashmir. People are not satisfied with the institutions dealing with handloom industry. Handloom

industry is suffering because no skilled labour force is available. Skilled and unskilled labour used to endlessly flow to the state from other parts of the country and now the same has emaciated to a noteworthy extent. Because of armed conflict, many people from Kashmir have migrated to other parts of the country and as a consequence they and their future generation shall certainly suffer from the crisis. Handloom sector is the main source of income for the common people and its backbone of the country's economy but armed conflict has radically and significantly eclipsed it. Handloom sector is an old age industry of the state; it is spine of arts and crafts and other industrial activity carried in Jammu and Kashmir. Kashmir has been famous throughout the world for producing good quality of handloom, items like, silk, pashmina shawls, kanishawls, tweeds, patoos, etc. Pashmina weaving is now rare; it is a good-looking fibre which is woven into delicate yarn; it is very costly and of very lofty quality. The yarn is in analogous in weight, warmth and softness. Handloom sector plays a decisive role in the economy of the state and this sector is job and export oriented. The state and central government also started huge training programme and policies, so as to provide infrastructure for the development of this sector. Handloom weaving being the oldest conventional crafts of Jammu and Kashmir state has earned universal standing for higher quality goods. The sector is spread throughout the valley and other rearward and hilly areas of the state. Kashmir, since times immemorial, has enjoyed worldwide renown for novelty of her industrial manufacturers and the beautiful quality of her arts and crafts. In ancient days, world looked to Kashmir for supply of premium quality of handloom products like paper, silk and woollen textiles.

Conclusion

The present study we can concluded that the handloom sector of Jammu and Kashmir is an vital sector contributing to overall development of current and other allied sectors in terms of affluence and employment creation .the handloom industry, the major segment in the unorganized sector plays a very important role in the economy of Jammu and Kashmir, It is agrobased and highly labour intensive and low capital investment. Handloom sector have gigantic potentials of job creation and development of rural/semi-urban areas they make use of more unskilled labour force and have direct on poverty mitigation. Handloom industry in Jammu and Kashmir has always been a hub of attraction. It is because bandage styles have an essence of magnetism in them that people tend to adopt some or the other trend on every occasion. Handloom industries can help a lot in this respect by providing forward and backward linkages with husbandry, manufacturing and the mainstay of the economy. In an overpopulated country like India every sector has got its own importance. Over populated country wants to generate employment for his enormous unemployed labour force. It has been seen that handloom industry got its importance in whole India in generating employment and income due to its labour intensive nature and need less investment which is manageable for everyone, so this sector is so fruit full for the overpopulated country like India. We need to have give full attention towards this eco friendly sector to generate the employment for over unemployed educated youth.

Reference

- Lavanya, L. k., Madhavaiah, C., and Murthy (2008). B.E. V.V.N Small scale Entrepreneurship in India. *Serbian Journal of Management*, Vol. 3, No. 2. pp 171-187
- Raveendra, N. R. and vankata, R.P and Harsha (2013). V.B.M Handloom Market (Need for Market Assessment, Problems and Marketing Strategy). *International Journal of Emerging Research in Management and Technology*, Vol. 2 No. 5, pp 6-11
- Sharma.R (2012). Problems and prospects of small scale industrial units. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Management Review*, Vol. 1 No. 2 pp 191-210
- kaushik, N. and Madhur, J.R. (2015). Impact of Government Schemes on Handloom Weavers At Maheshwar, M.P. *International Journal of Management Studies* Vol. 2 No 1, pp 27-36
- M. Towseef (2014). Handicraft production and employment in India: Economic analysis. *Global Journal of Human-Social Science: E Economics*, Vol. 14, No. 4, pp 26-31.
- B.B, Chopade (2013). Growth and Sickness of Small scale industries in India. *World Research Journal of Economics*, Vol. 2 No 1, pp 22-24
- Ranbir, S.Y. (2012) Research prospective for Small scale industries in India. *International Journal of Latest Research in Science and Technology*, Vol.1 No. 1 pp 70-75
- Surya, K.P Handloom industry in India: A study (2015). *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, Vol. 2 No 1 pp 24-29
- Bhutani, P. and Matta, J.M (2014), The Indian Handloom: Boom to the nation in Jeopardy. *International Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 2 No. 5 pp 248-251
- Ahmad Fayaz, and Negroo Asif Hussain (2013). An Analysis of Handloom Sector of Jammu and Kashmir: A case study of District Budgam. *International Journal of Management and Business Studies*. Vol: 3 pp: 106-109.
- Bhutani Priyanka, Matta Mitu, G (2014). The Indian Handloom: Boom to the nation in jeopardy. *International Journal of Business and Management*. Vol: 2 pp: 248-251.
- Kumar P, Surya (2015). Handloom industry in India: a Study *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*. Vol: 2 pp: 24-29.
- Kaushik Nikhil, Jain Madhur Raj 2015). Impact of Government Schemes on Handloom weavers at Maheshwar, M.P. *International Journal of Management Studies*. Vol:11 pp: 27-36.
- Dar Bilal Ahmad, and Bhat Fayaz Ahmad (2013). Small Scale Industries in Jammu and Kashmir (J&K): Growth, Performance and Challenges *International NGO Journal*. Vol: 8 pp: 38-43.
- B.Chopade B. (2013). Growth and Sickness of Small-Scale Industries in India *World research Journal of economics*. Vol: 2 pp: 22-24